

Ultrasonic study of vanadium myristate in liquor ammonia

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Abstract : The ultrasonic velocity of vanadium myristate confirms that there is a significant interaction between the solute-solvent molecules in dilute solutions and the carboxylate molecules do not aggregate appreciably in dilute solutions. The value of Critical Micelle Concentration (CMC) for vanadium myristate is in agreement with those obtained from other physical parameters. The effects of concentration and chain length of soap on ultrasonic velocity and the various acoustic parameters (adiabatic compressibility, specific acoustic impedance, intermolecular free length, apparent molar compressibility, apparent volume, molar sound velocity, molar sound compressibility and solvation number) have been investigated.

Keywords : Vanadium myristate, ultrasonic velocity, liquor ammonia, acoustic parameters.

Introduction

Metal soaps have recently become increasingly important in technological and academic fields. The physico-chemical characteristics and structure of the soap can be controlled up to an extent by the method and conditions of their preparation, and the studies are therefore of great significance for uses of the soaps in various industries under different conditions.

The ultrasonic velocity technique has been used to determine the nature of molecular interaction in various systems¹⁻¹⁴.

The present work deals with the study of ultrasonic measurements of aqueous solutions of vanadium myristate at different temperatures (303 K, 313 K, 323 K). The work has been initiated with a view to study the micellar behaviour, soap-soap and soap-solvent interaction and evaluate various acoustic parameters and to study the effects of concentration and chain length of the soap on these parameters.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of B.D.H./A.R. grade. Vanadium myristate, was prepared by direct metathesis of the corresponding potassium soap with slight excess of the solutions of vanadium pentoxide at 50–55 °C under vigorous stirring. Liquor ammonia of S. grade 0.91 was procured from Qualigens Fine Chemicals.

The purity of the soap was checked by determination of their melting points.

The ultrasonic measurements of the solution of vanadium myristate were carried out with a multifrequency ultrasonic interferometer (Model F-81, Mittal Enterprises, New Delhi) at a frequency of 1 MHz at different temperatures (303 K, 313 K and 323 + 0.05 K). The uncertainty of velocity measurements is 0.2%.

Calculations :

The ultrasonic velocity (v), specific acoustic impedance (z)¹⁵, adiabatic compressibility (β)¹⁶, molar sound compressibility (W)¹⁷, intermolecular free length (L_f)¹⁸, apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_k)¹⁹, apparent volume (ϕ_v), molar sound velocity (R)²⁰ and solvation number (S_n), were calculated by using the following relationships :

$$\beta = v^{-2}\rho^{-1} \quad (1)$$

$$Z = v\rho \quad (2)$$

$$L_f = (\beta/K)^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

$$\phi_k = 1000/C\rho_0(\rho_0\beta - \beta_0\rho) + \frac{M\beta_0}{\rho_0} \quad (4)$$

$$\phi_v = 1000/C\rho_0(\rho_0 - \rho) + \frac{M}{\rho_0} \quad (5)$$

$$R = \bar{M}/\rho v^{1/3} \quad (6)$$

$$W = \bar{M}/\rho\beta^{-1/7} \quad (7)$$

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$$\bar{M} = n_0M_0 + nM/n_0 + n \quad (8)$$

$$S_n = n_0/n[1 - \bar{V}\beta/n_0V_0\beta_0] \quad (9)$$

where V_0 , V , ρ_0 , ρ , β_0 , β are the ultrasonic velocity, density, adiabatic compressibility of the solvent and solution, respectively n_0 , n and M_0 , M are the number of moles and molecular mass of solvent and solute respectively, K is the temperature dependent Jacobson's constant, and C is the molar concentration of solution in mol m^{-3} .

Results and discussion

The ultrasonic velocity, v of the solution of vanadium myristate in liquor ammonia increases with increasing soap concentration (Table 1). The variation of ultrasonic velocity, with soap concentration, C can be expressed in terms of the concentration derivatives of density, ρ and adiabatic compressibility, β by the relationship¹⁶,

$$\frac{dv}{dc} = \frac{V}{2} \left(\frac{1}{\rho} \left[\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial c} \right] + \frac{1}{\beta} \left[\frac{\partial \beta}{\partial c} \right] \right)$$

Table 1. Ultrasonic velocity and acoustic parameters of vanadium myristate in liquor ammonia at different temperatures (303 K, 313 K, 323 K)

Sr. No.	$C \times 10^3$ (mol m^{-3})	$C^{1/2} \times 10^2$	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$ (kg m^{-3})	V (m s^{-1})	$\beta \times 10^{10}$ ($m^2 N^{-1}$)	L_f (Å)	$Z \times 10^{-3}$ (kg $m^{-2} s^{-1}$)	$\phi_v \times 10^6$ ($m^3 mol^{-3}$)	$-\phi_k \times 10^7$	$R \times 10^4$	$W \times 10^4$	S_n
Temp. 303 K												
1.	1.0	3.15	0.9101	1002.4	9.541	38.01	9.123	604.10	36.33	7.278	14.048	47.97
2.	2.0	4.46	0.9102	1004.2	9.521	37.96	9.141	604.10	33.32	7.286	4.662	43.62
3.	3.0	5.47	0.9106	1005.3	9.506	37.93	9.155	642.94	29.68	7.294	14.078	39.25
4.	4.0	6.32	0.9110	1007.3	9.485	37.89	9.175	633.22	31.80	7.301	14.091	41.80
5.	5.0	7.06	0.9112	1008.7	9.465	37.85	9.194	604.11	32.32	7.306	14.103	42.16
6.	6.0	7.73	0.9117	1011.5	9.435	37.78	9.22	584.69	33.67	7.313	14.116	43.85
7.	7.0	8.35	0.9121	1014.0	9.405	37.73	9.248	554.17	35.52	7.321	14.129	46.11
8.	8.0	8.92	0.9123	1016.3	9.378	37.66	9.271	545.85	35.25	7.327	14.142	45.62
9.	9.0	9.48	0.9123	1019.6	9.340	37.62	9.303	526.42	37.51	7.334	14.157	48.63
10.	10.00	10.00	0.9126	1022.8	9.312	37.55	9.334	510.91	37.02	7.340	14.166	47.68
Temp. 313 K												
1.	1.0	3.15	0.9102	1004.0	9.525	37.96	9.137	722.53	47.387	7.306	14.094	61.03
2.	2.0	4.46	0.9104	1006.6	9.494	37.91	9.166	729.52	40.387	7.315	14.107	52.21
3.	3.0	5.47	0.9108	1008.2	9.473	37.86	9.183	729.53	40.721	7.325	14.116	51.97
4.	4.0	6.33	0.9111	1010.0	9.443	37.81	9.202	729.54	41.388	7.332	14.143	52.88
5.	5.0	7.06	0.9114	1012.5	9.406	37.73	9.227	705.95	41.827	7.342	14.157	53.16
6.	6.0	7.73	0.9118	1016.2	9.368	37.65	9.267	690.21	47.453	7.354	14.181	60.57
7.	7.0	8.37	0.9123	1020.0	9.338	37.58	9.305	678.98	49.614	7.366	14.200	63.36
8.	8.0	8.94	0.9127	1023.6	9.298	37.51	9.342	670.55	52.360	7.377	14.222	66.95
9.	9.0	9.48	0.9132	1026.4	9.266	37.45	9.372	677.10	51.920	7.383	14.240	66.45
10.	10.0	10.00	0.9134	1029.7	9.230	37.38	9.407	658.80	51.210	7.400	14.300	65.22
Temp. 323 K												
1.	1.0	3.15	0.9104	1004.6	9.519	37.96	9.142	780.28	49.146	7.214	13.940	56.39
2.	2.0	4.46	0.9105	1008.2	9.477	37.87	9.180	778.91	46.807	7.225	13.959	53.99
3.	3.0	5.47	0.9110	1011.4	9.441	37.81	9.212	776.02	49.587	7.235	13.977	57.19
4.	4.0	6.33	0.9114	1014.4	9.402	37.72	9.242	770.70	53.354	7.248	14.001	62.09
5.	5.0	7.06	0.9118	1018.7	9.362	37.64	9.287	750.11	50.992	7.256	14.007	59.02
6.	6.0	7.73	0.9121	1022.6	9.314	37.55	9.327	745.61	55.540	7.270	14.041	64.37
7.	7.0	8.37	0.9126	1026.4	9.270	37.47	9.366	658.47	60.910	7.286	14.066	70.78
8.	8.0	8.94	0.9135	1030.0	9.231	37.38	9.402	650.77	64.353	7.300	14.094	74.98
9.	9.0	9.48	0.9136	1034.2	9.185	37.28	9.448	648.10	69.715	7.316	14.124	81.17
10.	10.0	10.00	0.9140	1037.8	9.144	37.21	9.482	645.11	68.731	7.326	14.135	80.02

The result indicates that the density increases while the adiabatic compressibility decreases with increasing soap concentration and so the quantity $[\partial\rho/\partial c]$ is positive while $[\partial\beta/\partial c]$ is negative. Since the values of $(1/\beta[\partial\beta/\partial c])$ are larger than the values of $(1/\rho[\partial\rho/\partial c])$ for the soap solution, the concentration derivative of velocity, (dv/dc) is positive which is in agreement with the results of other workers reported for electrolytic solution²¹⁻²³.

The plots of ultrasonic velocity, v vs soap concentration, C (Fig. 1) for solutions of vanadium myristate show a break at a definite soap concentration corresponds to the CMC of vanadium myristate at different temperatures (303 K : 5.45×10^{-3} , 313 K : 5.95×10^{-3} , 323 K : 6.45

where G is the Garnsey's constant. The value of Garnsey's constant G have been determined from the slope of the plots of v vs C for dilute solution below the CMC. The values of Garnsey's constant G at different temperature (303 K : 1463, 313 K : 2030, 323 K : 2950) and ultrasonic velocity of solvent are found to be higher for solution in liquor ammonia.

The adiabatic compressibility, β for the solution of vanadium myristate decrease with increase in soap concentration (Table 1). The decrease in adiabatic compressibility is attributed to the fact that the soap molecules in dilute solution ionize in simple metal cations, V^{5+} and myristate anions ($C_{13}H_{27}COO^-$). These ions in solution

Fig. 1. Ultrasonic velocity vs soap concentration.

$\times 10^{-3}$ mol m^{-3}). The plots of ultrasonic velocity vs soap concentration (C) have been extrapolated to zero soap concentration and the extrapolated values of ultrasonic velocity (303 K : 1003.2, 313 K : 1004.0, 323 K : 1004.6 $m s^{-1}$) are in agreement with the experimental values of ultrasonic velocity at different temperature (303 K : 1003.9, 313 K : 1004.8, 323 K : 1005.0 $m s^{-1}$) in the solvent mixture. The variation of ultrasonic velocity, v with soap concentration, C for dilute solution follows the relationship,

$$V = V_0 + GC$$

are surrounded by a layer of solvent molecules, firmly bound, and oriented towards the ions. The orientation of solvent molecules around the ions is attributed to the influence of electrostatic field of ions and thus the internal pressure increases, which lowers the compressibility of solution i.e. the solutions become harder to compress²⁴. The plots of adiabatic compressibility β vs soap concentration, C indicate a break at a definite soap concentration, which corresponds to the CMC of the vanadium myristate. The plots of β vs C are extrapolated to zero soap concentration and the extrapolated values of adiabatic compressibility, β_0 at different temperature (303 K :

9.56×10^{-10} , 313 K : 9.58×10^{-10} , 323 K : $9.59 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2 \text{ N}^{-1}$) are in close agreement with the experimental values of adiabatic compressibility for the solvent mixture at different temperature (at 303 K : 9.63×10^{-10} , 313 K : 9.64×10^{-10} , 323 K : $9.6 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2 \text{ N}^{-1}$).

The results of adiabatic compressibility have been explained in terms of Bachem's²⁵ equation,

$$\beta = \beta_0 + AC + BC^{3/2}$$

where A and B are constant and C is molar concentration of vanadium myristate (mol m^{-3}).

The constants A and B have been determined from the intercept and slope of the plots of $(\beta - \beta_0)/C$ vs $C^{1/2}$ and the values of A at different temperatures (303 K : -37.2×10^{-10} , 313 K : -53.6×10^{-10} , 323 K : -56.5×10^{-10}) are lower while those of B (303 K : 136×10^{-10} , 313 K : 278×10^{-10} , 323 K : 208×10^{-10}) are higher in liquor ammonia.

The intermolecular free length, L_f decreases while specific acoustic impedance, Z increases with the increase in soap concentration (Table 1), which can be explained on the basis of lyophobic interaction between the soap and solvent molecules which increases the intermolecular distance leaving relatively wider gaps between the molecules and thus becoming the main cause of impediment to the propagation of the ultrasound waves²⁶.

The plots of intermolecular free length L_f vs soap concentration, C and specific acoustic impedance, Z vs soap concentration, C show a break at a definite soap concentration, which corresponds to the CMC of vanadium myristate.

The apparent molar volume is related to soap concentration, C by the relationship²⁷,

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^0 + S_v C^{1/2}$$

where ϕ_v is limiting apparent molar volume and S_v is a constant. The plots of ϕ_v vs $C^{1/2}$ are linear which indicates that the equation is applicable for solution of vanadium myristate in liquor ammonia. The values of constant S_v (303 K : 0, 313 K : 0, 323 K : -18.7×10^{-4}) and limiting apparent molar volume ϕ_v (at 303 K : 655×10^{-6} , 313 K : 760×10^{-6} , 323 K : $810 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) have been determined from the slope and intercept of plots of ϕ_v vs $C^{1/2}$. The values of ϕ_v^0 and constant S_v at different temperature are found to be higher in liquor ammonia. The decrease in the values of ϕ_k and ϕ_v at higher soap concentration ($> 0.005 \text{ m}$) may be explained on the basis of close packing of ionic head groups in the

micelles, resulting in increase ionic repulsion and finally internal pressure.

It follows from Gucker's limiting law²⁸ by using Debye-Hückel theory²⁹⁻³³, that the apparent molar compressibility, ϕ_k is related to concentration, C by relationship,

$$\phi_k = \phi_k^0 + S_k C^{1/2}$$

where ϕ_k is the limiting apparent molar compressibility and S_k is constant. The plots of apparent molar compressibility, ϕ_k vs square root of soap concentration, $C^{1/2}$ are linear for dilute soap solutions. The values of constant, S_k (at 303 K : 15.3×10^{-5} , 313 K : 2.9×10^{-5} , 323 K : 1.9×10^{-5}) and limiting apparent molar compressibility ϕ_k^0 (at 303 K : 48.5×10^{-7} , 313 K : -56.0×10^{-7} , 323 K : -58.0×10^{-7}) have been obtained from the slope and intercept of plots ϕ_k vs $C^{1/2}$ (Table 1).

The value of the constant S_k is high while of ϕ_k^0 is low in liquor ammonia. The positive of S_k signifies a considerable soap-solvent interaction in the dilute solution of vanadium myristate.

The values of molar sound velocity, R , and molar sound compressibility, W for solutions of vanadium myristate increases with the increasing soap concentration (Table 1). The plots of R vs C and W vs C show a break at a definite soap concentration which corresponds to the CMC of vanadium myristate. The values of CMC are in agreement with the values obtained from other parameters.

The solvation number, S_n for solution of vanadium myristate in liquor ammonia increases with increase in concentration (Table 1) and decrease of chain length of the soap. The plots of solvation number vs soap concentration show break at definite soap concentration which corresponds to the CMC of the soap.

It is concluded that there is a significant interaction between the solute-solvent molecules in dilute solutions and the carboxylate molecules do not aggregate appreciably in dilute solutions. The values of CMC for vanadium myristate are in agreement with those obtained from other physical parameters.

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References

1. P. Tuomikoski and V. Nurmi, *Comment Phys. Maths.*, 1940, **10**, 11.
2. M. V. Kaulgrd, *Acoustica*, 1960, **10**, 316.
3. C. V. Chaturvedi and S. Prakash, *Acoustica*, 1972, **27**, 248.
4. P. Sitaramswamy, *J. Phys. Soc. Jpn.*, 1967, **23**, 1148.
5. E. Kawalska, W. Kowalski, C. Mazanek and M. Bodzed, *Rocz. Chemii.*, 1966, **40**, 469.
6. E. Kawalska, W. Kowalski and C. Mazanek, *Proc. Vib. Problem*, 1963, **2**, 4.
7. V. I. Surovtsev, V. M. Shevchenco, E. Govrenbein, Ya, and V. S. Raevskii, *Zh. Fiz. Khim.*, 1972, **46**, 2530.
8. B. M. Grinberg and V. I. Cbraztestva, *Prien. Ultraakust, Issled Vesschestva No.*, 1967, **23**, 128.
9. P. G. I. Fogg, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 411.
10. N. Prasad and S. Prakash, *Acoustica*, 1976, **36**, 313.
11. K. Gopal and N. P. Rao, *Acoustics Letters*, 1981, **4**, 164.
12. F. Franks, M. A. J. Quickenden, D. S. Reid and B. Watson, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1970, **66**, 583.
13. D. Sette, *Ricerca Sci.*, 1955, **25**, 576.
14. A. Dijavanbakht, J. Cong and R. Zana, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1977, **81**, 2620.
15. I. E. Elipiner, "Ultrasound Physical, Chemical and Biological Effects", Consultants Bureau, 1964, 371.
16. B. Jacobson, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1952, 61485.
17. S. Sindhu, "Ultrasound Velocity Studies in Liquids and their Correlation with the Structural Aspects", Gian Publishing Housing, Delhi, 1989.
18. W. Schaaf, *Z. Phys.*, 1947, **114**, 110.
19. A. Waissler *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1947, **114**, 110.
20. A. Pasynskii, *Acta Physico Chem. (URSS)*, 1938, **8**, 357; *J. Phys. Chem. (URSS)*, 1938, **11**, 451.
21. S. Prakash and C. V. Chaturvedi, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, **10**, 669.
22. K. Ramabraham and M. Suryanarayana, *Indian J. Pure Appl. Phys.*, 1998, **6**, 422.
23. I. G. Mikhailov M. V. Rozina and V. A. Shutilov, *Akust Zn.*, 1964, **1**, 213.
24. S. Prakash, F. M. Icinæoria and J. D. Pandey, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, **58**, 3078.
25. C. Bachem, *Z. Physik*, 1936, **101**, 541.
26. H. Eyring and J. F. Kincaid, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1938, **6**, 620.
27. D. O. Masson, *Phill. Mag.*, 1928, **8**, 218.
28. F. T. Gucker, *Chem. Re.*, 1933, **13**, 111.
29. P. Devye and E. Z. Hückel, *Physik*, 1923, **24**, 185.
30. K. N. Mehrotra, A. Kumar and S. P. Verghese, *Polish J. Chem. (Poland)*, 1994, **68**, 807.
31. K. N. Mehrotra, A. Kumar and S. P. Verghese, *Tenside Surf. Detg. (Germany)*, 1999, **36**, 210.
32. K. N. Mehrotra, A. Kumar and S. P. Verghese, *Tenside Surf. Detg. (Germany)*, 1999, **37**, 249.
33. K. N. Mehrotra, A. Kumar and S. P. Verghese, *Tenside Surf. Detg. (Germany)*, 2000, **3**, 39.